

Studies on the Extractive Behaviour of 12-Heteropoly Acids.

Part I : Extraction of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid.*

V. I. Lakshmanan and B. C. Haldar

The extraction of 12-tungstophosphoric acid ($H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$) into various organic solvents has been studied using P-32 or W-185. The order of extraction by the oxygenated organic solvents is given by $AmAc < NB \sim EtAc < MIBK < MEK < IsoAmOH < OctOH < BuOH$ which follows the order based on solubility of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ in these solvents except that methyl ethyl ketone occupies lower position in the extraction series compared to its position in the solubility series. Equilibria involved in the extraction process are discussed and the extraction constants have been calculated. The results of present study seem to indicate that the oxygenated organic solvents extract $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ from aqueous solution in the form of solvated ion pairs. From 0.5 M LiCl solution, the salt $LiH_2PW_{12}O_{40}$ is extracted into these solvents.

A critical survey of literature reveals that the extractive behaviour of 12-heteropoly-acids into organic solvents has not been studied in detail, though these acids are known to be extracted into oxygenated organic solvents and the extractions of P(V), Si(IV), As(V), etc., in the form of heteropoly-acids are frequently utilized in the analytical chemistry¹. The extraction chemistry of complex metal acids such as $HFeCl_4$, $HInBr_4$, etc., have received considerable attention in recent years and the results of extraction studies have provided useful information regarding extraction mechanism²⁻⁴. It is, therefore, considered worthwhile to investigate the extraction of 12-tungstophosphoric acid into organic solvents. Solvents selected include hydrocarbons, chlorinated hydrocarbons, ketones, alcohols, esters, etc. Ethers are not included in the present study because they often form three liquid phases with aqueous solutions of 12-heteropoly-acids and so interpretations of experimental data become difficult. Attempts have been made in this investigation to correlate the extractive behaviour of 12-tungstophosphoric acid to the characteristic properties of the solvents such as basicity, dielectric constant, etc.

1. G. H. Morrison and H. Freiser, "Solvent Extraction in Analytical Chemistry", John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York (1957).
2. R. M. Diamond and D. G. Tuck, "Extraction of Inorganic Compounds into Organic Solvents", *Prog. in Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, 2, 110.
3. H. A. Hermann, H. Irving, I. Rosenthal, J. F. Suttle, V. R. Usdin, A. R. Weiss, R. J. P. Williams, "Separation Methods in Analytical Chemistry", Interscience Publishers, John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1961.
4. a) T. J. ConoeChioli, M. B. Tocher and R. M. Diamond, *J. Phy. Chem.*, 1965, 1106, 69.
b) J. J. Bucher and R. M. Diamond, 1965, 1565, 69.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Activity was measured on a thin end-window type G.M. counter in operation with a stabilized high-voltage power supply and a dekatron scaler.

Conductance measurements were carried out at room temperature ($28^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$) using conductivity bridge, Type C, 101-102 of Toshniwal Instruments, Bombay, an internal oscillator, and a sensitive magic eye detector. The cell constant of the conductivity cell was 0.469.

Absorbance was measured on a Hilger and Watts ultraviolet spectrophotometer employing 1 cm silica cell. A Elico pH meter LI 10, manufactured by Electronic and Industrial Instruments Co., Hyderabad, was used for pH measurements.

Radio-isotopes and counting equipments were obtained from Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Trombay.

A.R. grade reagents and chemicals were used. Solvents were distilled in an all glass apparatus and the fractions boiling within $\pm 1^{\circ}$ to their boiling points were collected and used for extraction studies.

12-Tungstophosphoric acid labelled with P^{32} or W^{185} was prepared by adding 2 ml. of P^{32} or W^{185} to the initial reaction mixture of 8 g. of disodium phosphate ($Na_2HPO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$) and 50 g. of sodium tungstate in 75 ml. of boiling, and following the procedure described by Rosenheim and Jaenicke⁵ for the preparation of inactive 12-tungstophosphoric acid. The strength of stock solution of 12-tungstophosphoric acid was checked by estimating phosphorus as magnesium pyrophosphate and tungsten as oxinate⁶. Precautions were taken to prepare dust-free solution to avoid reduction of tungsten (VI).

All extraction experiments were performed at least in duplicate, but more often in higher multiplicates.

Extraction Procedure : 5 ml. of solution containing known amount of 12-tungstophosphoric acid were taken in a 100-ml open mouth separatory funnel. It was treated with hydrochloric acid, if necessary, to adjust the acidity of the solution and diluted to 25 ml with water. After equilibrating with an equal volume of organic solvent for two minutes, the two phases were allowed to separate. It was observed that the extraction was independent of equilibration time over the period 2-15 min. The top layer was first pipetted out without disturbing the bottom layer which was then removed by opening the stop-cock. Each solution was centrifuged and an aliquot was evaporated to dryness for activity measurements with a thin end-window G.M. counter. Corrections for back-ground, coincidence, self-absorption and self-scattering, whenever necessary, were applied. The sum of the activity in the aqueous and organic phase was $100 \pm 2\%$. The extraction coefficient, E , was calculated

5. A Rosenheim and J. Jaenicke, *Z. Anorg. Allgem. Chem.*, 1917, **101**, 25.

6. A Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", London, Longmans Green and Co., 1959.

from the relation,

$$E = \frac{\text{Activity in 1 ml of organic phase}}{\text{Activity in 1 ml of aqueous phase}}$$

The reproducibility among replicates was always within 7%.

Solubility measurements : A saturated solution was prepared by shaking for 5 min. excess of solid 12-tungstophosphoric acid with the organic solvent in a stoppered bottle maintained at 30°. The bottle was then kept in a thermostat at $28^{\circ} \pm 1^{\circ}$ for 15 min. with occasional shaking. The solution was found to attain equilibrium within 15 min. It was quickly filtered and an aliquot of the filtrate was analysed for tungsten by the oxinate method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical analyses (Table I) of the two phases obtained after equilibrating an aqueous solution of 12-tungstophosphoric acid with an equal volume of methyl ethyl ketone or ethyl acetate indicate that the ratio of W to P in both the phases remains the same and is found to be 12. The spectra (Fig. 1) of the aqueous phase before and after extraction are identical

Fig. 1. Ultraviolet spectra of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid.

- 1) 1.73×10^{-5} M of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid in ethyl acetate.
- 2) 2.24×10^{-5} M of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid in equilibrated ethyl acetate. λ_{\max} : 265 m μ .
- 3) 1.0×10^{-5} M of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid in water.
- 4) 1.29×10^{-5} M of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid in equilibrated aqueous phase.
- 5) 1.05×10^{-5} M of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid reextracted from ethyl acetate into water.
 λ_{\max} : 250 m μ .

and show maximum absorption at 250 $m\mu$. This peak is observed at 265 $m\mu$ in ethyl acetate solution of 12-tungstophosphoric acid. In the extraction with ethyl acetate, the organic phase also shows absorption maximum at 265 $m\mu$ which appears at 250 $m\mu$ in the aqueous solution of re-extracted 12-tungstophosphoric acid. It may, therefore, be inferred that the extracted species in the oxygenated organic solvents is 12-tungstophosphoric acid.

TABLE I

Analyses of Organic and Aqueous Phases after Extraction of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid with Organic Solvent

Solvent	Phase	Molar Conc. of P.	Molar Conc. of W.	Ratio of W : P
MEK	Organic	2.30×10^{-3}	2.76×10^{-1}	12.0
	Aqueous	7.40×10^{-3}	8.75×10^{-2}	11.9
EtAc	Organic	2.83×10^{-3}	3.41×10^{-2}	12.1
	Aqueous	2.16×10^{-2}	2.6×10^{-1}	12.0

Kerker and Matijevic⁷ have concluded from the results of light scattering experiments that 12-tungstophosphoric acid exists in organic solvents as $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$, though it behaves as a strong electrolyte in aqueous solution and its crystal structure is described as an aggregate of units (H_3+29H_2O) and $(PW_{12}O_{40})^{3-}$. However, the molar conductance (43.4 mhos) of dilute solution ($3.26 \times 10^{-4}M$) of 12-tungstophosphoric acid in nitrobenzene corresponds close to the values (24–38 mhos) reported for 1 : 1 electrolytes⁸. This implies ionization of the acid into H^+ and $H_2PW_{12}O_{40}^-$ in nitrobenzene solution.

TABLE II

Extraction Coefficients of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid between Organic Solvent and Aqueous Solution

Initial concentration of 12-tungstophosphoric acid = $6.1 \times 10^{-3}M$. Temperature = $28^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

Solvent	Extraction Coefficient (E)
Ortho-dichlorobenzene	$< 4.1 \times 10^{-5}$
Chloroform	$< 2.0 \times 10^{-5}$
Carbon tetrachloride	$< 2.0 \times 10^{-5}$
Benzene	$< 2.18 \times 10^{-5}$
Amyl acetate (AmAc)	1.1×10^{-2}
Nitrobenzene (NB)	3.1×10^{-2}
Ethyl acetate (EtAc)	3.2×10^{-2}
Methyl ethyl ketone (MEK)	1.5
Methyl isobutyl ketone (MIBK)	0.11
Iso-Amyl alcohol (IsoAmOH)	1.8
Octanol (OctOH)	2.2
Butanol (BuOH)	2.4

- M. Kerker and E. Matijevic, Proceedings of the VIIth International Conference on Co-ordination Chemistry, Stockholm and Uppsala, 1962, 4D₃.
- R. A. Robinson and R. H. Stocks, "Electrolytic Solutions", London, Butterworth Scientific Publications, 1959.

The results in Table II reveal that 12-tungstophosphoric acid ($\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$) is not extracted into non-oxygenated organic solvents such as benzene, carbon tetrachloride, etc., while it is extracted into oxygenated organic solvents which possess a basic group through which solute-solvent interaction can easily occur. These results seem to suggest that the oxygenated organic solvents extract $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ in the form of solvated ion pairs. It may be argued that the extraction should then depend upon the basicity of the solvent. However, the basicity of the solvent as measured by the shift in the infrared absorption band of CH_3OD ⁹ gives the order.

Solvent : NB < MIBK = MEK < EtAc < AmAc

(28) < (77) = (77) < (84) < (90)

which is different from the extraction order observed experimentally

AmAc < NB \sim EtAc < MIBK < MEK < IsoAmOH < OctOH < BuOH.

The order of extraction into organic solvents remains the same whether an aqueous solution of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ is extracted with an oxygenated organic solvent or a solution of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ in oxygenated organic solvent is equilibrated with water. The difference between the order based on the basicity of solvents and that observed on the basis of extraction into oxygenated organic solvents is not surprising in view of the fact that solvation by organic solvent depends not only on the basicity of the solvent but also on the steric availability of donor atom in solvent molecule. Further, the extraction of solvated ionic species is expected to be influenced by the dielectric constant of the solvent.

It is interesting to note that the solubilities of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ in the oxygenated organic solvents studied give the series :

Solubility in :	AmAc	NB	EtAc	MIBK	IsoAmOH
g.mole/l. at :	(0.023)	< (0.0146)	< (0.031)	< (0.043)	< (0.063)
28° :	< OctOH	< BuOH	< MEK		
:	(0.073)	(0.08)	(0.171)		

which almost follows the series based on the extraction into these solvents, except that methyl ethyl ketone occupies different positions in the two series. The higher solubility¹⁰ of methyl ethyl ketone in water compared to that of other solvents may be responsible for its lower position in the extraction series, because solvation of protons by organic molecules in the aqueous phase can lower the extraction of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ into the organic phase. Solvation of anions by alcohols may also cause better extraction of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ into isoamyl alcohol, octanol and butanol than into methyl ethyl ketone.

9. W. G. Gordy, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, **7**, 93.

10. International Critical Tables of Numerical Data, Physics and Technology, McGraw Hill Book Company, Inc., New York, Vol. III, 1929.

The extraction of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ into methyl ethyl ketone shows first order dependency (Fig. 2) on the hydrogen ion concentration of the equilibrated aqueous phase. The value of $\log E/(H^+)$ (Table III) is found to be independent of initial concentrations of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$. It is therefore reasonable to conclude that $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ exists in monomeric form in both the bases, in agreement with the observation of Kerker and Matijevic⁷.

Fig. 2. Effect of hydrogen ion concentration on the extraction coefficient of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid between organic solvent and aqueous solution.

- MEK : Initial concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid.
 ⊙ $3.3 \times 10^{-3} M$, Δ $5.7 \times 10^{-3} M$, \times $9.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, \otimes $2.45 \times 10^{-2} M$.
- EtAc : Initial concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid.
 ⊙ $5.7 \times 10^{-3} M$, \otimes $3.3 \times 10^{-3} M$, Δ $1.84 \times 10^{-2} M$, \square $6.2 \times 10^{-2} M$.
- MIBK : Initial concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid.
 ⊙ $6.13 \times 10^{-3} M$, \otimes $1.23 \times 10^{-2} M$, \times $1.84 \times 10^{-2} M$.
- NB : Initial concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid.
 ⊙ $5.97 \times 10^{-3} M$, \otimes $1.23 \times 10^{-2} M$.
- IsoAmOH : Initial concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid.
 ■ $6.13 \times 10^{-3} M$, \otimes $1.84 \times 10^{-2} M$.

Thus, the nett extraction equilibrium may be written as

and
$$K_1 = \frac{H^+(H_2PW_{12}O_{40}^-)_o}{(H^+)(H_2PW_{12}O_{40}^-)} = \frac{E}{(H^+)} \quad (1)$$

Subscript 'o' denotes organic phase and for the sake of simplicity, solvent molecules participating in the extraction process are not shown.

With ethyl acetate as an extractant, the plot (Fig. 2) of $\log E$ versus $\log (H^+)$ gives a straight line with a slope of two. Further, the values of $\log \frac{E}{(H^+)^2}$ (Table IV) do not appear to depend upon initial aqueous phase concentration of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ indicating that under the experimental conditions employed the extracted species in the organic phase is

TABLE III

Determination of Extraction Constant for 12-Tungstophosphoric acid

Solvent	Conc. of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid (in molarity)	$\log E$	Logarithm of Extraction constant $\log K = \log \frac{E}{(H^+)^2}$
MEK	2.86×10^{-3}	0.12	3.00
	6.13×10^{-3}	0.19	2.80
	1.23×10^{-2}	0.34	2.87
	1.84×10^{-2}	0.35	2.60
	2.45×10^{-2}	0.43	2.60
EtAc*	7.10×10^{-4}	-0.24	3.10
	1.42×10^{-3}	0.24	3.52
	3.55×10^{-3}	0.55	3.65
	7.10×10^{-3}	0.75	3.73
	1.40×10^{-2}	0.91	3.73
MIBK*	7.10×10^{-4}	0.05	3.52
	1.42×10^{-3}	0.39	3.88
	3.55×10^{-3}	0.63	3.79
IsoAmOH*	7.10×10^{-3}	0.90	3.99
	3.55×10^{-3}	0.54	4.07
	7.10×10^{-3}	1.05	4.26
	1.42	1.07	4.03

* Extraction carried out from 0.5 M LiCl medium.

monomeric in nature. A similar behaviour (Table IV; Figure 2) is observed in the extraction of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ with methyl isobutyl ketone and isoamyl alcohol. The extraction equilibrium may, therefore, be expressed by the relation,

and

$$K_2 = \frac{(H+H_2PW_{12}O_{40}^-)_o}{(H^+)^2(HPW_{12}O_{40}^{2-})} = \frac{E}{(H^+)^2} \quad (2)$$

TABLE IV

Determination of Extraction Constant for 12-Tungstophosphoric acid.

Solvent	Conc. of 12-Tungsto- phosphoric acid (in molarity)	log E	Logarithm of Extraction constant
			$\log K = \log \frac{E}{(H^+)^2}$
EtAc	6.13×10^{-3}	-1.49	2.90
	1.23×10^{-2}	-1.19	2.70
	1.84×10^{-2}	-0.93	2.60
	2.45×10^{-2}	-0.89	2.60
MIBK	6.13×10^{-3}	0.40	3.67
	1.23×10^{-2}	0.55	3.70
	1.84×10^{-2}	0.83	4.00
	2.45×10^{-2}	1.03	4.05
IsoAmOH	6.13×10^{-3}	0.25	4.96
	1.84×10^{-2}	0.46	4.65

In the extraction of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ by nitrobenzene, which has a high dielectric constant ($\epsilon = 36.1$ at 20°)¹¹, it is necessary to consider the ionization of the extracted species into the organic phase. Since it has been shown earlier from conductance measurements that $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ in nitrobenzene solution dissociates into H^+ and $H_2PW_{12}O_{40}^-$, the following equilibrium may be assumed to govern the extraction process :

and

$$K_3 = \frac{(H^+)_o (H_2PW_{12}O_{40}^-)_o}{(H^+)^2 (HPW_{12}O_{40}^{2-})} \quad (3)$$

In the extraction of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ from aqueous solution

$$(H^+)_o = (H_2PW_{12}O_{40}^-)_o \quad (4)$$

and

$$(H^+) = 2(HPW_{12}O_{40}^{2-}) \quad (5)$$

Combining equations 3, 4 and 5, one obtains

$$K_4 = 2K_3 = \frac{(H_2PW_{12}O_{40}^-)^2}{(HPW_{12}O_{40}^{2-})^2 (H^+)} = \frac{E^2}{(H^+)} \quad (6)$$

As predicted by equation 6, the agreement between the values (Table V) of $\log \frac{E^2}{(H^+)}$ calculated at two different concentrations of $H_3PW_{12}O_{40}$ is fairly good.

11. International Critical Tables of Numerical Data Physics, Chemistry and Technology, McGraw Hill Book Company, Inc., New York, Vol. VI, 1929.

Effect of hydrogen ion concentration has been studied by adding various amounts of HCl to the aqueous solution of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ and extracting it with nitrobenzene. It is verified that the extraction of HCl compared to that of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ is negligible. Equations (3) and (4) can be combined to give the expression

$$K_5 = \frac{(\text{H}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^-)_o^2}{(\text{H}^+)^2(\text{HPW}_{12}\text{O}_{40})} = \frac{E(\text{H}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40})}{(\text{H}^+)^2} \quad (7)$$

It follows from equation (7) that the plot (Fig. 3) of $\log E(\text{H}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^-)_o$ against (H^+) should give a straight line of slope equal to 2, as observed experimentally.

Fig. 3. Extraction of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid into Nitrobenzene as a Function of Hydrogen Ion Concentration. Concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid = $5.37 \times 10^{-3} M$. Slope = 2.0.

Considering the complexity of the aqueous chemistry of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$, it is surprising that the extraction of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$, though over limited $p\text{H}$ range, can be explained on the basis of simple equilibria described above. Extractions at higher $p\text{H}$ could not be studied because of decomposition of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$. The formation of precipitate did not permit to maintain the ionic strength of aqueous solutions constant by adding NaClO_4 or KCl . However, the extraction of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ from 0.5 M LiCl solution could be successfully carried out. The results (Tables II–V) show that the oxygenated organic solvents extract $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ better from 0.5 M LiCl solution than from aqueous solution. Analyses (Table VI) of organic extracts reveal that the extracted species contain Li, P, W in the proportion of 1 : 1 : 12 indicating the extraction of the salt $\text{LiH}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$. The extraction of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ from 0.5 M LiCl into methyl ethyl ketone does not depend upon the hydrogen ion concentration of the equilibrated aqueous phase while that into ethyl acetate, methyl isobutyl ketone and isoamyl alcohol shows first power dependency on the hydrogen ion concentration. Further, variations of initial aqueous phase concentration of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ from 1.42×10^{-3} – $1.42 \times 10^{-2} M$ for MEK, 7.1×10^{-4} – $1.42 \times 10^{-2} M$ for MIBK and EtAc and 3.5×10^{-3} – $1.40 \times 10^{-2} M$ for IsoAmOH do not appear to have any appreciable effect on its extraction

TABLE V

Determination of Extraction Constant for 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid.

Solvent	Conc. of 12-Tungsto- phosphoric acid (in molarity)	log E	[log K = log E]
MEK*	1.42×10^{-3}	1.59	1.59
	3.55×10^{-3}	1.60	1.60
	7.10×10^{-3}	1.58	1.58
	1.42×10^{-2}	1.57	1.57
			[log K = 2 log E]
NB*	7.10×10^{-4}	-1.16	-2.33
	1.42×10^{-3}	-1.16	-2.32
	3.51×10^{-3}	-1.17	-2.34
	7.10×10^{-3}	-1.15	-2.30
			$\log K = \log \frac{E}{(H^+)^{0.5}}$
NB	1.23×10^{-2}	-1.73	0.92
	1.84×10^{-2}	-1.53	0.82
	2.45×10^{-2}	-1.51	0.86

* Extraction carried out from 0.5 M LiCl medium.

TABLE VI

*Analyses of Organic Phase after Extraction of 12-Tungstophosphoric acid.**Concentration of lithium chloride = 0.5 M*

Solvent	Molar conc. of Li ⁺	Molar conc. of P(V)	Molar conc. of W(VI)	Ratio of Li ⁺ : P : W
MEK	2.0×10^{-2}	1.82×10^{-2}	2.19×10^{-1}	1.1 : 1 : 11.99
EtAc	1.3×10^{-2}	1.24×10^{-2}	1.49×10^{-1}	1.05 : 1 : 12.1

into these solvents. These observations can be explained by assuming the following extraction equilibria :

which are governed by the relations

$$K_6 = \frac{(\text{Li}^+\text{H}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40})_o}{(\text{Li}^+)(\text{H}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^-)} \quad (\text{for MEK}) \quad (8)$$

and

$$K_7 = \frac{(\text{LiH}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40})_o}{(\text{Li}^+)(\text{H}^+)(\text{HPW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{2-})} \quad (\text{for EtAc, MIBK and IsoAmOH}) \quad (9)$$

In the presence of excess (constant amount) of LiCl, which is not extracted into the organic phase, equations (8) and (9) can respectively be written as (10) and (11).

$$K_8 = K_6(\text{Li}^+) = E \quad (10)$$

$$K_9 = K_7(\text{Li}^+) = E/(\text{H}^+) \quad (11)$$

Fig-4.

Fig. 4. Effect of Hydrogen Ion Concentration on the Extraction Coefficient of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid between Organic Solvents and 0.5 M Lithium Chloride.

MEK : Initial Concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid
 $\times 1.42 \times 10^{-3}M$, ● $3.55 \times 10^{-3}M$, ○ $7.1 \times 10^{-3}M$, □ $1.42 \times 10^{-2}M$.

EtAc : Initial Concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid :
 $\times 1.42 \times 10^{-3}M$, ○ $3.55 \times 10^{-3}M$, ■ 7.1×10^{-3} , □ $1.4 \times 10^{-2}M$.

MIBK : Initial Concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid :
 $\times 1.42 \times 10^{-3}M$, ○ $3.55 \times 10^{-3}M$, ■ $7.1 \times 10^{-3}M$.

IsoAmOH : Initial Concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid :
 $\times 7.1 \times 10^{-3}M$, ○ $1.42 \times 10^{-3}M$.

NB : Initial Concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid :
 $\times 7.1 \times 10^{-4}M$, ● $1.42 \times 10^{-3}M$, ○ $3.51 \times 10^{-3}M$, □ $7.1 \times 10^{-3}M$.

Experimental data shown in Fig. 4 are in agreement with the predictions of equations (10) and (11).

With nitrobenzene as an extractant, the extracted salt is expected to ionize into Li^+ and $\text{H}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^-$ in the organic phase and so the extraction equilibrium may be represented as

and

$$K_{10} = \frac{(\text{Li}^+)_o (\text{H}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^-)_o}{(\text{Li}^+) (\text{H}^+) (\text{HPW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{2-})} \quad (12)$$

In the extraction of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ from 0.5 *M* LiCl solution, $(\text{Li}^+)_o = (\text{H}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^-)_o$, $(\text{H}^+) = 2(\text{HPW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{2-})$ and $(\text{Li}^+) = \text{constant}$. Under such conditions, the expression (12) reduces to

$$K_{11} = 2K_{10}(\text{Li}^+) = \frac{(\text{H}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^-)_o^2}{(\text{HPW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{2-})^2} = E^2 \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) is verified by the straight line graph in figure (4) which indicates that *E* is independent of initial concentration of $\text{H}_3\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ in the aqueous phase and *pH* of the equilibrated aqueous phase. If HCl is added to vary the *pH* of the aqueous phase, then $(\text{H}^+) \neq 2(\text{HPW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^{2-})$ and so equation (12) may be written as

$$K_{11} = \frac{E(\text{H}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^-)_o}{(\text{H}^+)} \quad (14)$$

where $K_{12} = K_{10}(\text{Li}^+)$.

Fig. 5. Extraction of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid into Nitrobenzene as a Function of Hydrogen Ion Concentration from 0.5*M* Lithium Chloride Media. Concentration of 12-Tungstophosphoric Acid = $2.05 \times 10^{-3}M$. Slope = 1.

Figure (5) shows a typical plot of $\log E(\text{H}_2\text{PW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}^-)_o$ versus $\log (\text{H}^+)$ for extraction of $\text{H}_3\text{FW}_{12}\text{O}_{40}$ from 0.5 *M* LiCl solution in which *pH* of the aqueous phase was adjusted with HCl. The slope of unity of the straight line graph is in accordance with equation (14).

In conclusion, it may be stated that the results of present investigation lends support to the view that 12-tungstophosphoric acid is extracted by oxygenated organic solvent in the form of solvated ion pair.

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Inorganic and Nuclear Chemistry Laboratory,
Institute of Science,
Bombay-32.

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